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A WIND FARM ANCILLARY SERVICE ALGORITHM WITH OPTIMAL FATIGUE DISTRIBUTION

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Liang Huang

Abstract

Ancillary services like inertial response and frequency support are crucial for power systems because they keep the power system stable, reliable, and resilient, especially as more renewable energy (like wind energy) replaces traditional power plants. However, when the wind turbine generators are equipped with the ancillary service function, they need to rapidly change the output power to support the grid frequency variation. As a result, the mechanical torque of the turbine side is changed dynamically. When a larger torque is added to the turbine's shaft, it might increase the mechanical stress and fatigue of the turbine, which eventually might reduce its lifetime. In order to analyse the impact of the grid-side ancillary service on the mechanical fatigue of the turbine, a full wind turbine generator model, including the aerodynamic wind turbine model, the drive train model, the permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) model, and the back-to-back converter model, is built initially in this task. Then, the two general types of converter control schemes (i.e., machine-side DC voltage control and grid-side DC voltage control) are applied to the developed full wind turbine model. Based on the simulation studies, test results demonstrate that the mechanical stresses by using both control methods are generally identical, but the machine-side DC voltage control leads to a slightly higher mechanical stress compared with the grid-side DC voltage control scheme. According to the above studies, the grid-side DC voltage control scheme with ancillary service is used to minimize fatigue. Besides, a wind farm ancillary service control algorithm based on high-speed side or low-speed side energy reservation is also developed. Finally, the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm is applied to a multiple-wind turbine system to show the effectiveness of the ancillary service function and fatigue optimization.

Ancillary service, DC voltage control, Energy reservation, Mechanical stress, Fatigue

1 INTRODUCTION

The escalating integration of renewable energy sources, particularly wind power, is fundamentally transforming modern power systems. As conventional synchronous generators are progressively displaced, the inherent stabilizing characteristics they provide—such as rotational inertia and primary frequency response—are significantly reduced. This transition poses substantial challenges to maintaining grid stability, reliability, and resilience, especially under conditions of sudden power imbalance. To address these challenges, ancillary services such as inertial response and frequency support have become increasingly critical. By enabling wind turbine generators to actively participate in frequency regulation, these services help sustain the secure operation of power systems with high renewable penetration.

However, the provision of such ancillary services introduces new technical challenges for wind turbine operation. In order to support grid frequency variations, wind turbine generators are required to rapidly adjust their output power. This dynamic response leads to corresponding fluctuations in the mechanical torque on the turbine shaft. When significant torque variations occur, they can impose increased mechanical stress and accelerate fatigue loading on critical components of the turbine. Over time, these effects may contribute to structural degradation and a reduction in the overall operational lifetime of the wind turbine. Therefore, while ancillary services from wind turbines are essential for grid stability, their impact on turbine structural integrity and durability must be carefully considered in both control strategy design and system operation.

To systematically investigate the impact of grid-side ancillary service provision on the mechanical fatigue of wind turbines, a comprehensive modelling framework is required. In this work, a full wind turbine generator model is developed, integrating the aerodynamic model of the wind turbine, the drive train dynamics, the permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), and the back-to-back power converter. This integrated approach enables a detailed representation of the interactions between the aerodynamic energy capture, mechanical power transmission, and electrical energy conversion processes, thereby providing a solid foundation for analysing the coupled electromechanical responses under frequency support operations. However, constructing such a full-scale wind turbine model presents significant challenges:

1. Multi-domain nonlinear coupling: The wind turbine system involves tightly-coupled nonlinear dynamics across aerodynamic, mechanical, and electrical domains, each operating on different time scales.
2. Simulation time-consuming: When the high-fidelity wind turbine mechanical model and the fast-switching electrical converter model are integrated together, the simulation is significantly time-consuming.
3. Fatigue representation: As mechanical fatigue is a relatively abstract concept, it is not easy to represent it quantitatively.

To address these challenges, the previously developed high-fidelity 3D wind turbine mechanical model is simplified to be a 1D momentum theory wind turbine model, while the detailed electrical converter model is used to guarantee the model accuracy. Besides, the mechanical torque is selected as an indicator to reflect the fatigue of the turbine, as they are highly relevant. Therefore, a key contribution of this work is finding a feasible way to translate the grid-

side ancillary service frequency response into mechanical-side fatigue representation, which helps perform a system-level estimation of the whole wind turbine generator or even the whole wind farm operation status.

Building upon the developed full wind turbine model, two widely adopted converter control strategies (namely, machine-side DC voltage control and grid-side DC voltage control) are implemented and evaluated under ancillary service operation. Through comprehensive simulation studies, the impacts of these control schemes on the mechanical behaviour of the turbine are systematically assessed. The results indicate that, although both control approaches yield broadly similar mechanical stress profiles, the machine-side DC voltage control strategy introduces slightly higher mechanical loading on the turbine components. This increased stress implies a greater contribution to fatigue accumulation over time when ancillary services are provided. According to the above studies, the grid-side DC voltage control scheme with ancillary service is used to minimize fatigue. Besides, a wind farm ancillary service control algorithm based on high-speed side or low-speed side energy reservation is also developed. Finally, the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm is applied to a multiple-wind turbine system to show the effectiveness of the ancillary service function and fatigue optimization. Hence, the developed ancillary service control strategy offers a pathway to harmonize power system stability and turbine lifetime considerations.

It is worth noting that the wind farm ancillary service control algorithm developed in this work has the ability to be embedded as an upper layer based on Deep Constraint Policy Optimisation (DCPO) within the multi-agent, multi-layer Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework developed in Task 2.2. The DCPO upper layer leverages the critic DNNs of the underlying robust residual DRL (RR-DRL) while incorporating the ancillary service requirement, so that frequency support can be provided while optimally and dynamically distributing fatigue among the turbines across the wind farm. Furthermore, the constraint-handling capability of DCPO ensures the operational safety of the wind farm during ancillary service provision. The integration of the proposed control algorithm with the wind farm wake model from Task 2.1 and the multi-synchronous-generator power grid model with AC and HVDC transmission (originally developed in the H2020 WinGrid project) enables two-way coupled simulations for control design and validation.

2 FULL WIND TURBINE MODELING

In previous tasks of the ICONIC project, the research topics are mainly on the mechanical part of the wind turbine generator (WTG), so the electrical part of the WTG is usually ignored. However, in order to link the wind farm and the power grid, the full WTG needs to be considered to evaluate the impact of the grid-side ancillary service on the mechanical-side fatigue. So, the full WTG model is considered in this task, and its structure is presented in Figure 1, which includes the wind turbine (WT), drivetrain, PMSG, back-to-back converter, and the power grid. The mathematical model of each part will be introduced step-by-step.

Figure 1. The full wind turbine generator structure including the electrical part and the mechanical part.

2.1 1D momentum theory-based aerodynamic WT model

In the initial stage of this task, the previously developed Open-FAST 3D WT mechanical model was integrated with the electrical converter model for simulation studies. However, due to the different time scales of the mechanical model and the electrical model (e.g., the power electronic converter works at the time scale of microseconds, while the 3D WT mechanical model works at the time scale of tens of seconds), the integrated WTG simulation model is significantly time-consuming.

To address the above challenge, a widely used simplified 1D momentum theory-based aerodynamic WT model is selected to represent the WT. Its expressions are listed below.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda = \frac{\omega_{WT} \cdot R_{WT}}{v_{wind}} \\ C_p(\lambda, \beta) = c_1(c_2\lambda_i^{-1} - c_3\beta - c_4) \cdot e^{-c_5\lambda_i^{-1}} + c_6\lambda \\ \lambda_i^{-1} = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{\beta^3 + 1} \\ T_{WT} = \frac{1}{\omega_{WT}} \cdot \frac{\rho A}{2} \cdot v_{wind}^3 \cdot C_p(\lambda, \beta) \\ \text{e.g., } c_1 = 0.518, c_2 = 116, c_3 = 0.4, c_4 = 5, c_5 = 21, c_6 = 0.007 \end{array} \right.$$

where R_{WT} denotes the radius of the turbine, ω_{WT} denotes the rotating speed of the turbine, λ denotes the tip speed ratio, β denotes the pitch angle, C_p denotes the power coefficient, and T_{WT} denotes the torque of the turbine.

Notably, the coefficients c_1 to c_6 vary by turbine design, but the typical values are listed together with the turbine expressions. According to the aerodynamic WT model and the typical parameters, the power coefficient-tip speed ratio curve can be obtained, which is presented in Figure 2. The power coefficient C_p represents the fraction of available wind power that is captured by the rotor, while the tip-speed ratio λ is the ratio between the blade tip speed and the incoming wind speed. For each given blade pitch angle β , the maximum power coefficient is determined by the rotating speed of the turbine blade.

Figure 2. The wind power coefficient-tip speed ratio curve.

2.2 Two-mass drivetrain model

In order to link the aerodynamic turbine model and the PMSG, a simplified two-mass drivetrain model is used to represent the dynamics of mechanical transmission systems in wind turbines. It captures the torsional dynamics between a high-inertia component (e.g., the wind turbine rotor) and a low-inertia component (e.g., the generator) connected by a flexible shaft. The expressions of the drivetrain model are listed below, where the gearbox is simplified as a ratio.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (T_{WT} - T_{shaft}) \cdot \frac{1}{J_{WT}} \cdot \frac{1}{s} = \omega_{WT} \\ (\omega_{WT} - \omega_{shaft}) \cdot \frac{1}{s} = \theta_{WT} - \theta_{shaft} \\ (\theta_{WT} - \theta_{shaft}) \cdot K_{stiff} + (\omega_{WT} - \omega_{shaft}) \cdot K_{damp} = T_{shaft} \\ \frac{\omega_{PMSG}}{K_{gear_ratio}} = \omega_{shaft}, \frac{T_{shaft}}{K_{gear_ratio}} = T_{PMSG} \end{array} \right.$$

where T_{WT} and T_{shaft} represent the torque of the turbine and shaft, J_{WT} represents the inertia of the wind turbine rotor, ω_{WT} and ω_{shaft} represent the rotating speed of the turbine and shaft, K_{stiff} is the coefficient of stiffness, K_{damp} is the damping coefficient, K_{gear_ratio} is the ratio of the gearbox, ω_{PMSG} represents the rotating speed of the PMSG rotor, and T_{PMSG} represents the torque of the PMSG.

2.3 Integration of wind turbine model

When connecting the aerodynamic model, the drivetrain model, the PMSG model, and the power converter model, the full WTG model is presented in Figure 3. Considering that the detailed PMSG and converter models have been standardized in the library of MATLAB/Simulink, it is not illustrated in detail. However, the basic dynamic relationship regarding torque, rotating speed, and current of the PMSG has been presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The integrated full wind turbine generator model.

Hence, a simplified but feasible full WT model linking the wind and the power grid is developed, which can translate the grid-side power response into the mechanical stress variation on the WT mechanical side. With the developed full WT model in Figure 3, all the dynamics, including the rotating speed and torque on the WT mechanical side, the DC link voltage, and the grid-side output voltage, current, and power, can be captured. Besides, due to the simplicity of the 1D WT model, the simulation speed is relatively fast and acceptable.

3 CONTROL SOLUTIONS WITH ANCILLARY SERVICE

In the previous section, a full WT model linking the wind and the power grid has been developed, which builds a foundation for this task. This section will move forward to the control solutions for the ancillary service function. More details will be illustrated as follows.

3.1 Typical converter control solution without ancillary service

In order to study the impact of the ancillary service on the WT, it is important to understand how to achieve the ancillary service from the converter level control and the wind farm level control. According to the literature review and discussion with other ICONIC project partners, it is known that there are two possible ways to change the operating point of the WT: one way is changing the rotating speed and torque of the generator by converter control, while the other way is changing the pitch angle of the turbine by pitch angle controller. Considering the fact that the grid-side electrical power response is much faster than the mechanical power response, changing the mechanical power by the pitch angle controller might be too slow to meet the inertia response requirement in the grid code. So, the pitch angle is assumed to be constant in this work, and the main research focus is on the converter control and energy reservation algorithm for adjusting the operating point on the power coefficient curve.

Figure 4. Typical converter control solution without ancillary service.

The typical converter control solution without ancillary service is presented in Figure 4, where CC denotes the current controller, RPC denotes the reactive power controller, DVC denotes the DC voltage controller, and the SC denotes the speed controller. In this typical control scheme, the DC voltage is controlled by the grid-side converter (GSC), and the mechanical speed or power is controlled by the machine-side converter (MSC). In this case, the output power of the WT will follow the power command given to the MSC controller. More specifically, the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm is typically applied to optimize the operating point by changing the power command. However, since the research focus in this task is mainly on ancillary service, which requires an energy reservation. So, when the ancillary service is considered, the real operating point on the power coefficient curve is lower than the MPP for energy reservation.

3.2 Grid-side DC voltage control with ancillary service

Based on the typical converter control solution introduced before, the different converter DC voltage control solutions with ancillary service will be studied in this subsection. Generally, in a PMSG-based wind turbine, the DC-link voltage can be controlled either by the GSC or the MSC. Grid-side control is the conventional approach, offering clear decoupling between machine and grid dynamics, reliable DC-link regulation, and strong capability for reactive power support and grid compliance, making it well-suited for utility-scale applications. However, it may be less responsive to fast mechanical variations and can be sensitive to weak grid conditions. In contrast, machine-side DC voltage control provides faster response to wind fluctuations and can perform better in weak or isolated grids, but it introduces coupling between DC voltage regulation and MPPT, potentially reducing energy capture efficiency.

In fact, ancillary service can be achieved based on both DC voltage control solutions. So, both solutions will be investigated. In this subsection, the grid-side DC voltage control with ancillary service will be introduced first.

Figure 5. Grid-side DC voltage control with ancillary service.

The grid-side DC voltage control with ancillary service is presented in Figure 5. The GSC control scheme includes inner-loop current controllers and an outer-loop DC voltage droop controller. The MSC control scheme includes inner-loop current controllers and an outer-loop active power controller. The key idea for achieving ancillary service is to add an f-P droop feedback on the power reference. The droop expression is listed below.

$$K_{droop} \cdot (f_N - f_{pll}) = \Delta P^*$$

When there is a frequency change on the power grid, the phase-locked loop (PLL) can capture the frequency variation in real time. Then, the f-P droop feedback term leads to the change of the power reference. For example, when the grid frequency reduces, it indicates that the power demand is higher than the power generation in the power system. Then, the f-P droop feedback term introduces a larger power reference to the WT. As the output power of the WT follows the power reference, additional power is injected from the WT to the power grid. So, this is exactly the ancillary service for the power grid.

3.3 Machine-side DC voltage control with ancillary service

The grid-side DC voltage control solution with ancillary service has been introduced in the previous subsection. Actually, the ancillary service can also be achieved by machine-side DC voltage control. So, the machine-side DC voltage control solution with ancillary service will be introduced in this subsection.

The machine-side DC voltage control with ancillary service is presented in Figure 6. The GSC control scheme includes inner-loop current controllers and an outer-loop active power controller. The MSC control scheme includes inner-loop current controllers and an outer-loop DC droop controller. The key idea for achieving ancillary service is to add an f-P droop feedback on the power reference. However, the power reference is given to the GSC controller instead of the MSC controller.

Figure 6. Machine-side DC voltage control with ancillary service.

As shown in Figure 6, the DC voltage of the converter is controlled by the MSC, which may lead to a different dynamic response compared with the GSC DC voltage control scheme. So, it is interesting to compare the two types of converter DC voltage control solutions with ancillary service to evaluate their impact on the mechanical fatigue of the WT. More specific simulation results will be presented and discussed in the next section.

3.4 A farm-level distributed control algorithm for ancillary service

In the previous subsections, two converter-level WT control solutions have been introduced. This subsection will move to a farm-level control algorithm for ancillary service.

Figure 7. Wind farm energy reservation scheme through changes in operating points.

When the WT needs to provide ancillary service, having sufficient energy reservation is a precondition. Figure 7 presents the basic idea of energy reservation. Namely, the real operating point is either on a higher-speed side or a lower-speed side to reserve energy.

Figure 8. Farm-level distributed control algorithm for grid ancillary service.

Moreover, a farm-level distributed control algorithm is presented in Figure 8. Firstly, the maximum power coefficient point is calculated according to the expression C_p . Then, the tip speed ratio is found for the maximum C_p . Subsequently, the equivalent rotating speed of the generator at the maximum power point can be calculated. Finally, the frequency droop control-based feedback term is used to modify the speed reference of the generator.

Notably, the developed farm-level ancillary service control algorithm is a fully distributed control scheme, which does not rely on a central controller. In other words, each WTG can work based on its local variables, such as wind speed, pitch angle, generator speed feedback, etc. This distributed control scheme can reduce the risk of malfunction of the wind farm during cyber-attacks (Notably, more details about cybersecurity studies are discussed in Task 2.6 of the ICONIC project).

4 RESULTS

In this section, the simulation studies of the developed full WT model with converter-level control solutions and farm-level control solutions will be carried out. Firstly, the two converter-level DC voltage control solutions with ancillary service will be compared regarding the fatigue estimation in single WT cases. Then, the two farm-level ancillary service control solutions will be tested on multiple WT cases.

4.1 Simulation settings

The WT model in this task is based on a representative 4 MW geared wind turbine with parameters aligned to modern commercial designs, such as the Vestas 4 MW platform (e.g., V117). The main parameters are reported in Table 1. The turbine features a rotor diameter of 117 m and operates with a rated rotor speed of 1.0 rad/s, corresponding to a generator speed of approximately 1050 rpm through a 100:1 gearbox. The aerodynamic performance is characterized by a cut-in wind speed of 3 m/s and a rated wind speed of 11 m/s, reflecting typical operating conditions for utility-scale turbines. The mechanical dynamics are modelled using a total rotor inertia of $4 \times 10^6 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$ and a generator inertia of $4 \times 10^4 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$. The electrical system is based on a 690 V generator connected to a full-scale power converter. Overall, these parameters are used in the developed WT model in this task.

Table 1: Main Parameters of Vestas-V117 Wind Turbine Model

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Power Rating	4 MW	Rotor diameter	117 m
Total rotor inertia	$4 \times 10^6 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$	Cut-in wind speed	3 m/s
Generator inertia	$4 \times 10^4 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$	Rated wind speed	11 m/s
Pole pairs	2	Rated rotor speed	1.1 rad/s
Gearbox ratio	100:1	Rated generator speed	1050 rpm (110 rad/s)
Rated AC voltage	690 V	Rated DC voltage	1500 V

4.2 Single wind turbine simulation with typical converter control solution with and without ancillary service

Firstly, simulation studies based on the typical control scheme shown in Figure 4 are carried out, and the two study cases with and without ancillary service are compared as follows.

Figure 9. Simulation results of a single WT model without ancillary service.

Figure 10. Simulation results of a single WT model with ancillary service.

Figures 9 and 10 present the simulation results of the developed 4MW WT model without and with ancillary service, respectively. The parameters of Vestas-V117 WT listed in Table 1 are used as a reference. Notably, in order to avoid a longer simulation time, the inertia of the WT is intentionally reduced to some extent.

As shown in Figures 9 and 10, the WT starts from 0s to 10s. During the 10s to 14s, the WT reaches a steady state. Then, the grid frequency is reduced by 0.5 Hz at the instant of 14s. When the ancillary service is not applied, the WT does not respond to the grid frequency variation, as shown in Figure 9. Differently, when the ancillary service is applied, the WT has a power response related to the grid frequency variation, as shown in Figure 10.

Through comparing the simulation results in Figures 9 and 10, it can be seen that when the WT outputs more power to support the grid frequency variation, both the accelerating torque of the PMSG and the total mechanical torque increase. In other words, the mechanical stress of the WT increases when the ancillary service is applied. It will increase the mechanical fatigue of the WT to some extent. Since the mechanical fatigue is an abstract concept, it is difficult to observe and analyze it quantitatively. So, to simplify the analysis, the mechanical

torque and the accelerating torque are used as indicators to reflect fatigue in this task. Based on the above analysis, it is revealed that the ancillary service can lead to the rise of mechanical stress as well as the increase in the mechanical fatigue of the WT to some extent.

4.3 Comparison of machine-side and grid-side DC voltage control solutions in single wind turbine study cases

According to previous studies, it is known that the ancillary service might lead to an increase in the mechanical fatigue of WT. This section will provide a more detailed quantitative analysis regarding two different converter-level ancillary service solutions.

Figure 11. Simulation results of a single WT model with an ancillary service solution achieved by grid-side DC voltage control.

Figure 11 and Figure 12 present the simulation results of the developed 4MW WT model with ancillary service solutions achieved by grid-side DC voltage control (i.e., the control solution in Figure 5) and machine-side DC voltage control (i.e., the control solution in Figure 6), respectively. As shown in Figures 11 and 12, the WT reaches a steady state before 14s. When the grid frequency is reduced by 0.5 Hz at the instant of 14s, WTs have power responses related

to the grid frequency variation. In both cases, more power is output from the WT to the grid, which helps maintain the power system frequency stability.

Figure 12. Simulation results of a single WT model with an ancillary service solution achieved by machine-side DC voltage control.

Through comparing the simulation results in Figures 11 and 12, it can be seen that when the WT outputs more power to support the grid frequency variation, the active power responses in the two cases are similar but slightly different. Specifically, the accelerating torque of the PMSG in Figure 12 is slightly higher than that in Figure 11, but the total mechanical torques of the turbines are basically identical. Hence, it indicates that the mechanical stress of the WT by using the MSC DC voltage control is slightly larger than that of the WT by using the GSC DC voltage control. Thus, the WT with the ancillary service achieved by the MSC DC voltage control may cause a more severe fatigue property, which may shorten the lifetime of the WT.

Overall, it is found that the ancillary service of the WT can be achieved by either the GSC DC voltage control or the MSC DC voltage control. These two control solutions have a similar impact on the mechanical fatigue of the WT. However, the ancillary service solution achieved by the MSC DC voltage control causes a slightly worse impact on the fatigue of the WT.

According to the previous simulation studies, the key simulation results can be summarized and compared for quantitative analysis. Table 2 lists the WT mechanical stress in several different study cases, where the accelerating torque and the total torque of the turbine during the frequency response period are used as indicators to evaluate the impact on mechanical fatigue approximately.

Table 2: WT mechanical stress comparison with different converter-level control solutions

Study cases	Selected ancillary service solutions	Maximum accelerating torque of the generator	Mechanical torque increase of the turbine
1	Typical solution without ancillary service	0 Nm	0 Nm
2	Typical solution with ancillary service	18 kNm	2 MNm
3	Ancillary service with GSC V_{dc} control	18 kNm	2 MNm
4	Ancillary service with MSC V_{dc} control	21 kNm	2 MNm

Comparing the four study cases in Table 2, it can be concluded that the ancillary service can cause a larger mechanical stress compared with the typical converter control solution without ancillary service. However, the mechanical torques caused by different converter-level ancillary service solutions are basically identical. The ancillary service with the MSC DC voltage control causes a slightly larger accelerating torque compared to the ancillary service with the GSC DC voltage control. So, from the perspective of an optimal fatigue distribution, the ancillary service achieved by the GSC DC voltage control is preferable to be used.

4.4 Comparison of different farm-level ancillary service control solutions in multiple wind turbine study cases

In the previous subsection, the impact of the ancillary service with two converter-level control solutions on fatigue is compared. The simulation results show that the ancillary service with the MSC DC voltage control scheme causes slightly larger mechanical torque than the ancillary service with the GSC DC voltage control scheme. So, the GSC DC voltage control scheme is preferable to be used in this subsection to minimize the mechanical fatigue.

The focus of this subsection is changed from the converter-level control to the farm-level control to analyse the impact of different ancillary service solutions. Section 3 introduces two possible energy reservation schemes of the WT. One is a high-speed side energy reservation scheme, while the other is a low-speed side energy reservation scheme. Figure 13 shows the simulation results using the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm with a low-speed side energy reservation scheme. Figure 14 shows the simulation results using the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm with a high-speed side energy reservation scheme. In each case, three WTs with different wind speeds are used as examples to show the effect of the ancillary service function under different conditions. It is worth mentioning that the pitch angle is used as a fixed pitch angle in these studies.

Figure 13. Simulation results of multiple WTs model with the developed wind farm ancillary service algorithm using a low-speed side energy reservation scheme.

Figure 13 shows the simulation results of three WTs using the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm with a low-speed side energy reservation scheme under different wind speed conditions. It can be seen that WT1, WT2, and WT3 work under 10 m/s, 8 m/s, and 6 m/s of wind speed conditions, respectively. Thus, WT1 has higher energy to support the grid when the grid frequency is reduced, while WT3 has lower energy to support the grid. When the WTs provide ancillary service (i.e., frequency support) to the grid, their mechanical torques increase slightly. So, the impact of the developed ancillary service control solution on fatigue is not obvious. However, a significant disadvantage of this solution is that when the grid frequency reduces, the output power of each WT decreases for a while initially and then increases. So, the frequency support from each WT has a delay.

Figure 14. Simulation results of multiple WTs model with the developed wind farm ancillary service algorithm using a high-speed side energy reservation scheme.

Figure 14 shows the simulation results of three WTs using the developed wind farm ancillary service control algorithm with a high-speed side energy reservation scheme under different wind speed conditions. Different from the simulation results in Figure 13, when the grid frequency reduces, the output power of each WT in Figure 14 increases immediately without any delay. So, it provides relatively fast frequency support to the grid. It means that the high-speed side energy reservation scheme is better than the low-speed side energy reservation scheme in terms of the power response speed. Moreover, when the WTs provide frequency support to the grid, their mechanical torques increase slightly. So, the impact of the developed ancillary service control solution on fatigue is not obvious.

Beyond the per-turbine fatigue mitigation discussed above, the multi-WT case also reveals an opportunity for fatigue distribution among the turbines at the farm level. Because WT1, WT2, and WT3 operate under different wind speeds (10, 8, and 6 m/s, respectively), they inherently have different reservoirs of kinetic energy and different available headroom for frequency support. Allocating a larger share of the ancillary service contribution to turbines with higher available energy (e.g., WT1) and a smaller share to turbines that are already more loaded or operating closer to their constraints (e.g., WT3) makes it possible to balance the additional mechanical loading across the farm rather than concentrating it on individual turbines. The proposed farm-level distributed control algorithm provides the structural basis for such allocation, and its potential integration with the DCPO upper layer of the DRL framework from Task 2.2 can enable an optimal and dynamic fatigue distribution among turbines under time-varying wind and grid conditions, while the constraint-handling capability of DCPO safeguards the operational safety of the wind farm.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work establishes a comprehensive yet computationally feasible framework to evaluate the impact of ancillary service provision on wind turbine mechanical fatigue by integrating aerodynamic, mechanical, and electrical dynamics into a unified model. The comparative studies demonstrate that the ancillary frequency support by the WTs can be achieved by different converter-level control strategies and farm-level control strategies. At the converter level, both GSC and MSC DC voltage control schemes deliver similar frequency support performance. However, the MSC-based approach results in a slightly higher generator accelerating torque, indicating a marginally greater fatigue impact. Consequently, GSC DC voltage control is the preferred converter-level solution from a fatigue mitigation perspective. At the farm level, both low-speed and high-speed side energy reservation schemes enable coordinated frequency support across multiple turbines while causing only minor increases in turbine mechanical torque. Nevertheless, the high-speed side energy reservation scheme offers a clear advantage by providing an immediate power response to frequency deviations, whereas the low-speed side scheme exhibits an initial delay. Therefore, considering both dynamic performance and mechanical stress, the combination of GSC DC voltage control and high-speed side energy reservation represents the most effective ancillary service solution for wind farm applications.